

Current Trends And Awareness Of Internet Of Things Using Research Scholars Of Alagappa Govt, Arts College: A Case Study

Dr.S.Muthuvennila¹, Dr.M.Muthumani²

¹Assistant Professor, PG & Research Department of Library and Information Science
Vellalar College for Women (Autonomous), Thindal, Erode.

²Founder Cum Librarian and Information Scientist,
V.V.A.M.U. Pandian Memorial Bhagat Singh Padippagam, Madurai.

Corresponding author- Dr.S.Muthuvennila

E-mail: muthuvennila.s28@gmail.com

Abstract:

This white paper uses the skills of researchers from the Alagappa Govt.Arts College of to discuss IoT awareness. The main objectives of this study are the frequency of use, perception, benefits, importance, usefulness of the Internet of Things, and the services that use the Internet of Things. The Internet of Things is now very popular and a current trend in the use of technology. The survey focused on 110 questionnaires, of which 67 were fully answered by the research scientist, 43 were incomplete with missing answers, and the IoT user's response rate was 60.9% of his. The majority of respondents using IoT are aware that faculty uses it, with male (6) and female (10) total respondents (16%). User awareness program with overall male (7) and female (8) respondents (15%). Most research scientists use his IoT awareness of 14 (20.9%) more informative.

Keywords: Internet of things, Awareness, Research scholars, Technology.

Introduction

The Internet these days occupies unique vicinity in diverse regions of human life. Its increase is fueled via way of means of mobile devices, which can be turning into increasingly part of cutting-edge existence as anybody desires to be continuously related to the net. This become made viable via way of means of the developing availability of low-fee high-velocity Internet get admission to, the supply of extra Wi-Fi-enabled devices, the accessibility of less expensive technology, and high-penetration Smartphone`s. Technological improvement has given us get admission to many offerings which include the look for Information, purchases, price tag bookings, navigation on maps, and verbal exchange through email, social networks, and cellular applications.

All of this brought about the net for verbal exchange and get admission to sure offerings through devices. But the following revolution wherein the net, like cellular phones, will take ubiquitous vicinity in our lives because it begins off evolved to attach matters with inside the bodily global and is anticipated to have a prime effect at the manner we live. It's referred to as the "Internet of Things (IoT)" and it is connecting everything, which may be something from mobile phones, espresso makers, cars, washing machines, air conditioners, lights, wearable devices, and something else you may assume.

Internet of Things (IoT) history

When Kevin Ashton was working on a project for Proctor and Gamble in the early 2000s to enhance supply chain management by connecting RFID data to the internet, he first put forth the idea of the Internet of Things (IoT). LG made plans for the first refrigerator with internet connectivity public

in January 2000. LG made plans for the first refrigerator with internet connectivity public in January 2000. The "Internet of Things" was mentioned in a study by the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) from 2005 that noted the "Internet of Things" progress. To encourage the adoption of Internet Protocol (IP) networking hardware in energy, consumer, medical, and industrial applications, the IPSO Alliance was established in 2008. IPv6 (Internet Protocol version 6) was released in 2012.

Review of literature:

Pujar & Satyanarayana (2015). This paper says that the "Internet of Things and libraries". The Internet has made a giant leap from the "Internet of Communications" to the "Internet of Things". This made it possible to connect things and transfer data with or without human intervention. It can revolutionize the way we live. Like other service industries, it has great potential to improve library services. Attempts to explain what the "Internet of Things" is, technology and its evolution, examples of service industries, consideration of potential implications for libraries, and guidance to the library sector that could be effectively implemented. The IOT has great potential for libraries. When implemented in a desirable way, it produces desirable results and adds value to library resources and services. It is still in the development stage and it makes sense to wait for librarians to familiarize themselves with this new technology and for it to become more widely accepted, adopted, implemented and better implemented in libraries. At the same time, it would be interesting to learn from the early adopter and develop better ways to maximize the benefits of his IoT adoption in the library. The library is subject to change and has been

around for quite some time, so IoT will be the next big thing after the internet.

NK (2019). This paper examines the “Internet of Things (IoT) in Academic Libraries”. The Internet has made a giant leap from the “Internet of Communications” to the “Internet of Things”. This made it possible to connect things and transfer data with or without human intervention. It can revolutionize the way we live. Like other service industries, it has great potential to improve library services. Attempts have been made to explain what the "Internet of Things" is, the technology and its evolution, with examples from the service industry and its potential impact on libraries and potential library areas where it can be effectively implemented.

Nag & Nikam (2016). This paper says that the “Internet of things applications in academic libraries”. We are entering a new era of information technology called the Internet of Things (IoT). IoT is coming as a wave of internet development. IoT has the potential to provide solutions that improve service efficiency and security in academic libraries. In this article, we discuss possible uses of IoT. In particular, we consider pressure sensors using cloud computing, magic mirrors, and wireless sensor network (WSN). With this in mind, we have developed an approach to improving library facilities and providing reader-friendly systems. This system is a step towards an intelligent library. This research introduces the concept of the Internet of Things to improve the service of academic libraries more efficiently. The Internet of Things is the ideal new technology to impact your customers by delivering new scalable and efficient services faster and easier. The proposed technology, cloud computing, magic mirrors and pressure measurement via wireless sensor networks, can improve resource utilization and increase cost efficiency by developing administrative services in university libraries.

Qin (2018). This paper examines the “The research of the library services based on internet of things”. The purpose of this article is to explore the scope and possible forms of use of Internet of Things technology in library services. Based on the analysis of the literature on this topic, the main areas of application of his IoT in commercial institutions were identified, the Anglo-Saxon literature for the period 2010-2017 was analyzed and the modern library services were defined. Compare the scope of commercial and non-profit activities to see if the areas where the commercial company is using or plans to use his IoT could inspire the library. Thus, a theoretical model was developed for his use of IoT in library activities. Research shows that IoT technologies could potentially be used in library services and other businesses in a similar way to

how they are implemented in the commercial sector. Using IoT in libraries is a new topic that has not yet been explored. In recent years, the potential application of this technology to the needs of libraries has been discussed at international conferences and has become an interesting topic for library associations. This indicates the importance of this topic for professionals. However, it is difficult to find comprehensive scientific studies on this subject.

Kaushik (2019). This paper says that the “Perceptions of library and information science professionals towards Internet of Things (IoT)”. The Internet of Things (IoT) is a hot topic all over the world, and it's spreading rapidly in many areas, such as libraries and computing. That's why librarians and computer scientists are fascinated by the Internet of Things (IoT). This survey aims to gather the views of librarians and computer scientists on the Internet of Things (IoT). The study found that most of the librarians and information scientists who participated in this study were from academic libraries, and that he spent two years researching the term librarian, a colloquial (IoT) concept from online sources. The biggest reason for not knowing the concept of (IoT) was seen as "Don't use this concept in the workplace." Additionally, the results demonstrated the need for specific training and the usefulness of Internet of Things (IoT) concepts. The ability to integrate many things through a single interface or device. This survey will help you gain insight into Internet of Things (IoT) concepts from library and information technology professionals and apply them to your library and technology community.

Objective of the study:

1. To determine the frequency of Internet of Things, Alagappa Govt. Arts College research students would be used.
2. To find out the Benefits of the Internet of Things as applied by research students from the Alagappa Government Arts College.
3. To Determine the Internet of Things awareness using research students from Alagappa Govt, Arts College.
4. To Know the Important Internet of Things research was conducted by Alagappa Government Arts College students.
5. To Know the Benefits of Internet of Things using Alagappa Govt, Arts College research students
6. To Identify the Internet of Things services using research students from Alagappa Government Arts College.

Methodology

This study acquires data on the internet of things from a survey conducted at the Alagappa Govt. Arts College. The survey was conducted for

scholarly research purposes only, and a total of 110 out of 67 respondents completed the questionnaires. The remaining 43 respondents chose not to respond. Using solely the arts, sciences, and management, I have chosen research scholars from 11 different departments. On the basis of the category's overall strength, care was made to choose a representative sample from each category for simple random selection. The data were gathered using a straightforward random sampling procedure. The data was subsequently examined using descriptive statistical techniques in conjunction with the internet of things.

Scope and Limitation of the study

I have chosen Alagappa Govt. Arts College Karaikudi, which is associated with Alagappa University, for the current study, which is exclusively open to research scholars. The study's objective was to use the internet of things and raise awareness of its advantages, significant benefits, and services. In Tamil, English, History, Economics,

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table: 1 Nativity wise distribution of the respondents * Gender wise distribution of the respondents Cross tabulation

S. No	Nativity wise distribution of the respondents	Gender wise distribution of the respondents		Total
		Male	Female	
1	Rural	9	12	21
2	Urban	10	15	25
3	Semi Urban	10	11	21
Total		29	38	67

This table displays the According to the percentage analysis, out of 67 respondents included for the study, 29 of them were male internet of things users

Commerce, Mathematics, Physics, Chemistry, Botany, Zoology, and Geology, I have chosen 11 research divisions. Researchers from Alagappa Govt. Arts College followed the study's survey and questionnaire methodologies for gathering data.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in Advantages of Internet of things with respect to Age of the respondents.
2. There is no significant difference in important using Internet of Things with respect to Frequency.
3. There is no significant difference in Benefits of using Internet of Things with respect to Frequency.
4. There is no significant difference in Services of using Internet of Things with respect to Frequency.
5. There is no significant difference in Problems of using Internet of Things with respect to Frequency.

in rural, urban, and semi-urban areas, and 38 were female respondents in these same areas.

Table: 2 Age wise distribution of the respondents * Name of the Faculty Cross tabulation

S. No	Age wise distribution of the respondents	Name of the Faculty			Total
		Arts	Science	Management	
1	Below 25 Years	3	0	1	4
2	26 – 28Years	11	9	0	20
3	29 – 31 Years	11	9	3	23
4	32-34 Years	6	7	2	15
5	Above 35 Years	2	2	1	5
Total		33	27	7	67

This table shows that the from the percentage analysis, it was found that out of 67 respondents Considered for the study using internet of things cross tabulation below 25 years in arts, science and management in 4, 26-28 years

respondents in arts, science and management in 20, 29-31 years of respondents in arts, science and management in 23, 32-34 years of respondents in 15, above 35 years of respondents in 5 using internet of things.

Table: 3 Name of the Faculty * Gender wise distribution of the respondents Cross tabulation

S. No	Name of the Faculty	Gender wise distribution of the respondents		Total
		Male	Female	
1	Arts	13	20	33
2	Science	12	15	27
3	Management	04	03	07
Total		29	38	67

This table demonstrates that, according to the percentage analysis, male respondents in the arts, sciences, and management made up 29 of the

67 respondents who were taken into account for the study using the internet of things.

Table: 4 Department wise distribution * Gender wise distribution of the respondents
Cross tabulation

S. No	Department wise distribution	Gender wise distribution of the respondents		Total
		Male	Female	
1	Tamil	3	6	9
2	English	5	4	9
3	History	2	5	7
4	Economics	3	5	8
5	Commerce	4	3	7
6	Mathematics	0	4	4
7	Physics	1	4	5
8	Chemistry	4	0	4
9	Botany	2	1	3
10	Zoology	2	4	6
11	Geology	3	2	5
Total		29	38	67

This table demonstrates that, according to the percentage analysis, the majority of the 67 respondents who were taken into account for the

study using the internet of things utilized Tamil and English 9, economics 8, history 7, and botany the least.

Table: 5 Frequency wise distribution of respondent's

S. No	Frequency of using	Frequency	Percent
1	Daily	4	6.0
2	weekly	19	28.4
3	Twice in a week	24	35.8
4	Monthly once	20	29.9
Total		67	100.0

From the percentage analysis, it was determined that out of 67 respondents who were taken into consideration for the study, the frequency

of IoT use was most frequently twice a week in 24 respondents (35.8%), once a month in 20 respondents (29.9%), once a week in 19 respondents (28.4%), and daily in 4 respondents (6.0%).

Table: 6 Time spent on searching internet * Gender wise distribution of the respondents
Cross tabulation

S. No	Time spent on searching internet	Gender wise distribution of the respondents		Total
		Male	Female	
1	Below 1 hour	5	5	10
2	1-2 hours	6	11	17
3	2-3 hours	12	13	25
4	Above 3 hours	6	9	15
Total		29	38	67

According to the percentage analysis, it was discovered that, of the 67 respondents who were taken into account for the study, 10 men and 17

women spent less than an hour using the internet of things, 17 men and 25 women spent between one and three hours using it, and 15, both men and women, spent more than three hours using it.

Table: 7 Awareness of using IoT * Gender wise distribution of the respondents Cross tabulation

	Awareness of using IoT	Gender wise distribution of the respondents		Total
		Male	Female	
	Library Professionals	1	2	3
	Faculty Members	6	10	16
	Orientation Programmes	7	4	11
	Seminar/conference	3	6	9
	User Awareness Program	7	8	15
	Trial and error method	5	8	13
	Total	29	38	67

This table demonstrates that, according to the percentage analysis, both male and female library professionals who were among the 67 respondents taken into account for the survey were aware of using the internet of things. 3, faculty members in both genders 16, orientation

programmes in both male and female 11, user awareness programmes in both male and female 15, trial-and-error methodology in both male and female 13, seminars/conferences in both male and female 9, and orientation programmes in both male and female 3.

Table: 8 Reasons for using IoT distribution of the respondents

S. No	Reasons for using IoT	Frequency	Percent
1	Easy to use	3	4.5
2	Less Expensive	9	13.4
3	More Informative	14	20.9
4	Global Research at one place	12	17.9
5	Time Saving	8	11.9
6	Easy to update	13	19.4
7	Effective Presentation	8	11.9
	Total	67	100.0

According to the percentage analysis, it was discovered that out of the 67 respondents who were taken into account for the study, the majority of respondents used the internet of things for reasons that included being more informative in 14, making updates simple in 13, conducting global research in one location in 12, and making it easy to use in 3 (4.5%).

Advantages of the IoT with respect to Age

The ANOVA test was carried out to identify whether there is significant difference in Advantages of Internet of things with respect to Age of the respondents.

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in Advantages of Internet of things with respect to Age of the respondents.

Table 9: ANOVA test- Advantages of the IoT with respect to Age

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Reduced costs	Between Groups	4.018	4	1.004	.740	.568
	Within Groups	84.162	62	1.357		
	Total	88.179	66			
Higher efficiency and productivity	Between Groups	12.783	4	3.196	2.385	.061
	Within Groups	83.068	62	1.340		
	Total	95.851	66			
More business opportunities	Between Groups	9.727	4	2.432	1.775	.145
	Within Groups	84.959	62	1.370		
	Total	94.687	66			
Improved customer experience	Between Groups	5.117	4	1.279	1.102	.364
	Within Groups	71.988	62	1.161		
	Total	77.104	66			
Increased mobility and agility	Between Groups	15.282	4	3.820	2.564	.047
	Within Groups	92.390	62	1.490		
	Total	107.672	66			
Make a Wide Variety of Content Access	Between Groups	7.612	4	1.903	1.380	.251
	Within Groups	85.463	62	1.378		

	Total	93.075	66			
Latest and updated	Between Groups	9.581	4	2.395	1.518	.208
	Within Groups	97.822	62	1.578		
	Total	107.403	66			
No Opening or Closing Hours	Between Groups	4.603	4	1.151	.801	.529
	Within Groups	89.039	62	1.436		
	Total	93.642	66			
Multiple and Simultaneous Access	Between Groups	5.762	4	1.441	.837	.507
	Within Groups	106.686	62	1.721		
	Total	112.448	66			
Library Management Automation	Between Groups	8.869	4	2.217	1.858	.129
	Within Groups	73.996	62	1.193		
	Total	82.866	66			

Interpretation

The estimated significance value for items 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10 in this table is larger than 0.05, indicating that the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the advantages of the internet of things with respect to age is accepted.

However, item 5's estimated significance value is less than 0.05 for all items, rejecting the null hypothesis that there is no difference between the advantages of the internet of things and age.

Important using Internet of Things with respect to Frequency

The ANOVA test was carried out to identify whether there is significant difference in important using Internet of Things with respect to Frequency

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in important using Internet of Things with respect to Frequency.

Table 10: ANOVA test- Important using Internet of Things with respect to Frequency

ANOVA		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Libraries provide free access to scholarly books	Between Groups	5.132	3	1.711	1.136	.342
	Within Groups	94.897	63	1.506		
	Total	100.030	66			
Journals	Between Groups	1.501	3	.500	.338	.798
	Within Groups	93.245	63	1.480		
	Total	94.746	66			
Newspapers	Between Groups	8.011	3	2.670	1.670	.182
	Within Groups	100.706	63	1.599		
	Total	108.716	66			
Encyclopedias and other	Between Groups	6.143	3	2.048	1.429	.243
	Within Groups	90.304	63	1.433		
	Total	96.448	66			
Print reference sources	Between Groups	5.805	3	1.935	1.236	.304
	Within Groups	98.643	63	1.566		
	Total	104.448	66			

Interpretation

This table demonstrates that the estimated significance value for items 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 is greater than 0.05, indicating that the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the importance of using the Internet of Things with respect to frequency is accepted.

Benefits of using Internet of Things with respect to Frequency

The ANOVA test was carried out to identify whether there is significant difference in Benefits of using Internet of Things with respect to Frequency

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in Benefits of using Internet of Things with respect to Frequency.

Table 11: ANOVA test- Benefits of using Internet of Things with respect to Frequency

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Use of smart devices	Between Groups	5.018	3	1.673	1.125	.346
	Within Groups	93.639	63	1.486		
	Total	98.657	66			
Achieve customer-centricity	Between Groups	2.577	3	.859	.493	.688
	Within Groups	109.721	63	1.742		
	Total	112.299	66			
Reduction in operational cost	Between Groups	9.355	3	3.118	2.344	.081
	Within Groups	83.810	63	1.330		
	Total	93.164	66			
Gathering rich data	Between Groups	5.330	3	1.777	1.053	.376
	Within Groups	106.312	63	1.687		
	Total	111.642	66			
Enhanced security measures	Between Groups	1.715	3	.572	.399	.754
	Within Groups	90.285	63	1.433		
	Total	92.000	66			

Interpretation

The estimated significance value for items 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 in this table is greater than 0.05, indicating that the null hypothesis that there is no appreciable difference in the advantages of using the Internet of Things with respect to frequency is accepted.

Services of using Internet of Things with respect to Frequency The ANOVA test was carried out to identify whether there is significant difference in Services of using Internet of Things with respect to Frequency

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in Services of using Internet of Things with respect to Frequency.

Table 12: ANOVA test- Services of using Internet of Things with respect to Frequency

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Providing access to traditional and online collections	Between Groups	2.814	3	.938	.646	.588
	Within Groups	91.485	63	1.452		
	Total	94.299	66			
Consulting training	Between Groups	4.382	3	1.461	1.066	.370
	Within Groups	86.304	63	1.370		
	Total	90.687	66			
Track and trace services	Between Groups	5.182	3	1.727	1.205	.315
	Within Groups	90.280	63	1.433		
	Total	95.463	66			
Sharing factual information	Between Groups	12.291	3	4.097	2.920	.041
	Within Groups	88.395	63	1.403		
	Total	100.687	66			
Providing directory information	Between Groups	.476	3	.159	.092	.964
	Within Groups	108.270	63	1.719		
	Total	108.746	66			

Interpretation

This table demonstrates that the estimated significance value for items 1, 2, 3, and 5 is greater than 0.05, indicating that the null hypothesis that there is no discernible difference between the services provided by the Internet of Things and respect to frequency is accepted. However, the null hypothesis is rejected because there is a significant difference in the services of using the Internet of Things with respect to frequency, as indicated by the

estimated significance value for item 4 being less than 0.05 for all the items.

Problems of using Internet of Things with respect to Frequency The ANOVA test was carried out to identify whether there is significant difference in Problems of using Internet of Things with respect to Frequency

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in Problems of using Internet of Things with respect to Frequency.

Table 13: ANOVA test- Frequency of using Internet of Things with respect to Frequency

		ANOVA				
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Retrieval of too much of irrelevant information	Between Groups	.605	3	.202	.118	.949
	Within Groups	107.305	63	1.703		
	Total	107.910	66			
Unavailability of Internet connection	Between Groups	1.418	3	.473	.306	.821
	Within Groups	97.239	63	1.543		
	Total	98.657	66			
Downloading is delay	Between Groups	5.165	3	1.722	1.032	.385
	Within Groups	105.133	63	1.669		
	Total	110.299	66			
Lack of search skills	Between Groups	17.638	3	5.879	3.821	.014
	Within Groups	96.929	63	1.539		
	Total	114.567	66			
The information is not constantly available on the same URL	Between Groups	1.860	3	.620	.481	.696
	Within Groups	81.125	63	1.288		
	Total	82.985	66			
6. Slow internet speed	Between Groups	11.827	3	3.942	2.245	.092
	Within Groups	110.621	63	1.756		
	Total	122.448	66			
No proper guidance and training	Between Groups	3.645	3	1.215	.757	.523
	Within Groups	101.132	63	1.605		
	Total	104.776	66			

Interpretation

This table demonstrates that the estimated significance value for items 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, and 7 is greater than 0.05, indicating that the null hypothesis that there is no discernible difference in the problems associated with using the Internet of Things with respect to frequency is accepted.

However, item 4's estimated significance value is less than 0.05 for all items, rejecting the null hypothesis that there is no difference between the frequency and problems associated with using the internet of things.

Conclusions:

Now a day's one of the most current trends in internet of things implementation for libraries, to improve the access to collections of sources available for libraries, stock control and recommendation & services, Mobile phone/ Cellular IoT Connectivity, technologies' and location based services, cost of savings, safety, Monitoring, drones, smart door locks and survey patrons. The internet of things (IoT) current trends and technology that use for libraries, library staff and faculty members also should be improve the services. Today's libraries community hubs and innovation and technology for look extra like community hubs and locations fully interested. The IoT superior form the convergence of technology, micro electro mechanical systems (MEMS), and the Internet. The use of current trends and awareness of using internet of things in learning while obtaining modern technology is awareness is discussed in this article for research scholars. Conducting more awareness programme, conference and workshops related to internet of things.

Suggestions:

1. Create Awareness through seminars and work shop for internet of things.
2. Provide Library technical and advanced innovations tools.
3. Organize more programmes in higher educations to create awareness and current technology.
4. Technical sessions for staff and research scholars will improve the research purpose.

Reference:

1. Kaushik, A. (2019). Perceptions of library and information science professionals towards Internet of Things (IoT). *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1-13.
2. Nag, A., & Nikam, K. (2016). Internet of things applications in academic libraries. *International Journal of information technology and library science*, 5(1), 1-7.
3. NK, S. (2019). Internet of Things (IoT) in Academic Libraries.
4. Pujar, S. M., & Satyanarayana, K. V. (2015). Internet of Things and libraries. *Annals of Library and Information Studies (ALIS)*, 62(3), 186-190.
5. Qin, J. (2018, May). The research of the library services based on internet of things. In *4th International Symposium on Social Science (ISSS 2018)* (pp. 399-407). Atlantis Press.